

Effectiveness of Structured – Teaching Programme on the Influence of Maternal Diet on Breastfeeding among Lactating Mothers Admitted at Mapims, Melmaruvathur

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Abstract:- The present study was assess the pre-test knowledge, evaluate the effectiveness of a structured – teaching program on the influence of maternal diet and associate post-test knowledge with the selected demographic variables. The study was used a pre-experimental one group pretest –post-test research design. The sample size was 20 selected by convenience sample technique, primi mother admitted in MAPIMS, Melmaruvathur. Pre test knowledge was assessed, provide structured- teaching program and after assessed post test knowledge on maternal diet. There was a statistically significant difference between pretest and posttest mean knowledge score with the “t” value 29.82 at <0.000 level of significance. Hence structured teaching program on maternal diet was effective in increasing the knowledge among primi lactating mothers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human milk is the most appropriate of all available milk for human infants and its specific to him/her needs. It provides complete nutrition to infants during the first 6 months of life. Lactating mothers need to eat a balanced diet with vitamins and minerals. Breastfeeding mothers should eat enough food-balanced diets when they are hungry. But many mothers may not care to take a balanced diet. So, it's essential to educate mothers to go for simple and healthy meals that include choices from the entire recommended group from the food pyramid. The nutrient needs of the mother during breastfeeding include an increased need for energy, vitamins, minerals, water, and iron supplements may be necessary.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has championed breastfeeding through the Innocenti Declaration. Baby Friendly Hospital Initiative and the International Code of Marketing of Breast Milk Substitutes. The WHO global target of 2025 aims to increase the rate of exclusive breastfeeding in the first 6 months by at least 50%. Furthermore, a reduction in low birth weight and child malnutrition can be addressed primarily by breastfeeding. Breastfeeding needs to be sustained up to 2 years of life – exclusively for the first 6 months of life, before introduce of complementary feeding.

Breast milk is the best food for newborns and infants. The nutritional stores of a lactating woman may be more or less depleted as a result of the pregnancy and loss of blood during childbirth. Lactation raises nutrition needs, mainly because of the loss of nutrients, first through colostrums and breast milk. The diet of the mother increased during breastfeeding carbohydrates, protein, fat, calcium and iron, vitamin A, vitamin D, and thiamine. Mothers should not receive less than 1800 calories per day.

➤ *Statement of the problem*

A study to assess the Effectiveness of a structured – teaching program on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among lactating mothers admitted at MAPIMS, Melmaruvathur.

➤ *Objectives*

- To assess the pre-test knowledge regarding the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among lactating mothers.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of a structured – teaching program on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among lactating mothers.
- To associate post-test knowledge with the selected demographic variables such as the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among lactating mothers.

➤ *Hypotheses*

- *H1* – The post-test knowledge of breastfeeding mothers who had structured – teaching programs regarding the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding will be higher than in the pre-test – knowledge.
- *H2*- There will be an association between the post-test – knowledge with selected demographic variables.

➤ *Assumption*

- Latching mothers have inadequate or less knowledge of the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among latching mothers.
- A structured teaching program will enhance the knowledge on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among latching mothers.

➤ *Delimitations*

- The period of the study is limited to 4 weeks.
- Mothers are available during the study period.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research approach adopted in the present study was a pre-experimental one group pretest –post-test research design was used. The sample size was 20 selected by convenience sample technique. The study was conducted the primi mother who has admitted to Melmaruvathur Adhiparasakthi Institute of Medical Science at Melmaruvathur. A structured questionnaire and planned health teaching program were developed with the help of related review and discussion with subject experts. The reliability and validity of the questionnaires were established. The questionnaire consists of 32 questions with the maximum score of 24. The questionnaires consist of demographic variables and structured interview questionnaire on maternal diet on breastfeeding. Pretest was conducted by giving a structured 25 close-ended objective type questionnaire developed by the investigator. For each correct answer, score 'one' was given and for the wrong answer, score 'zero' was given. Based on the score, the level of knowledge was categorized as Inadequate

knowledge (0-8), Moderate adequate knowledge (9-17), and Adequate knowledge (18-25) on the same day providing a structured- teaching program 30 minutes regarding maternal diet on breastfeeding using a flash card. After four days, the post- test was administered to the same mothers for 20 to 30 minutes.

III. RESULTS

Demographic characteristics of the samples about mother's education 14(70%) of them were illiterate, and 1(5%) of them had completed primary school. 4 (20%) had middle school and only 1 (5%) of them had higher secondary education. Among the mothers 14(70%) were coolie, 4(20%) of them were house wife and 1(5%) were government employee. About socio-economic status, 17(85%) mothers had a family income less than Rs. 10000, 2(10%) mothers had a family income of Rs. 10001 – 12000, 1(5) mothers had a family income of Rs. >15000. Regarding religion 17 (85%) were Hindu and 3(15%) were Muslim respectively, and Christians were nil. Further regarding their residence 8(40%) mothers were living in rural areas, 4(20%) mothers were in an urban area and 8(40%) mothers were living in semi-urban.

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Level of Knowledge score on the Influence of Maternal Diet on Breastfeeding among Lactating Mothers in Pre and Post-Test N=20

S.NO	KNOWLEDGE	PRE- TEST		POST -TEST		signif
		frequency	%	frequency	%	
1.	Inadequate ≤ 50	20	100	0	0	
2.	Moderate Adequate 51-74%	0	0	7	35	
3.	Adequate ≥ 75	0	0	13	65	
	Total	20	100	20	100	

Table 1 depicted that the knowledge of mothers on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding before the structured – teaching program was 100% inadequate. After the structured teaching program, the knowledge became adequate at 65%. Moderately adequate 35% and there was nobody with inadequate knowledge.

Table 2 Comparison of the Mean and Standard Deviation of Knowledge Score Regarding the Influence of Maternal Diet among Latching Mothers in the Pre and Post-Test

Group	Mean	SD	t- value	P- value
Pre-test	6.95	2.30	29.82	<0.000(S)
Post –test	25.6	2.81		

S- Significant

Table 2 depicted that the mean knowledge score in the pre-test was 6.95 with a standard deviation of 2.30. in the post-test the mean score was 25.6 with a standard deviation of 2. 81. The improvement was statically tested by paired "t" test and the result was found to be significant (P< 0.001). The result indicated that the structured teaching program was effective to improve the knowledge level of lactating mothers.

IV. CONCLUSION

The present study assessed the effectiveness of a structured teaching program on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding among lactating mothers. The study finding highlights knowledge was increased through a structured teaching program. It was recommended that the nursing personnel update their knowledge on the influence of maternal diet on breastfeeding. The nurses should educate regularly use the structured teaching program on the influence of maternal diet on feeding which in turn will minimize the morbidity and mortality rate of both baby and mother.

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